

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375595482>

"The Humanistic Transformation in Health Coaching: a new pragmatic role for Ethics"

Conference Paper · June 2023

CITATIONS

0

READS

8

1 author:

Stefano Luca Patania

Associazione Italiana Health Coaching

4 PUBLICATIONS 1 CITATION

SEE PROFILE

"The Humanistic Transformation in Health Coaching: a new pragmatic role for Ethics"

Stefano Luca Patania

AIHC Scientific Committee Member

International Erich Fromm Society Member

Abstract

In a recent discussion within the Italian Health Coaching Association (AIHC), the importance of re-establishing the foundations of the identity of the Health Coach emerged, with the aim of an approach that sees as a priority the interest of the well-being of the person. It was like the Health Coaches were followers of a shift given by some progressive applied facilitation techniques and lacking a humanistic concept that could clearly guide a natural human transformation.

In fact, according to the discussion in the Coaching Labs, the methodological setting of coaching techniques appeared to be mainly based on Performance. There seemed to be a lack of a rational basis of the profession that would inspire the Coach in interpreting ethical dilemmas in the Client-Society relationship. They felt incomplete as Health Coaches because they lack a core identity in their methodological approach. This methodological deficiency in the past often caused a superficial and harmful management of the value system of the individual and of the communities and companies in coaching support, negatively affecting personal and organizational wellbeing.

The philological research carried out by the AIHC scientific committee confirmed with its own observation the scheme proposed by Iordanou et al. related to the ethical shift of coaching techniques in healthcare systems. To the vision of the ethical shift our observation added elements of merit not addressed before and a more ontological and humanistic interpretation.

Our research selected the main protagonists of this ethical shift in Coaching to understand the overall nature of the phenomenon, positioning them along the distribution of the various types of coaching formed, going back to the first authors of the Coaching methodology.

A further observation revealed how the general foundations of the method were compatible in general with the thinking of the exponents of the "third force" of psychology, and in particular Erich Fromm, the only one to rigorously and completely address the ethical analysis of the personal development dynamics. From our point of view, what makes Fromm the reference for Health Coaching is that through the objective humanistic ethics, he demonstrates his full faith in human nature and links it to the development of potential and well-being. From one hand he support the natural trend of humankind to be productive and healthy. On the other hand, he exactly describes the polarity between individual and society as a dynamic tension between two forces: the performance required of the individual by the social system, and the person's tendency to one's wellbeing, from an ethical point of view.

The past attempt of coaching techniques in the ethical shift has been to resolve this tension, mostly by promoting performance. We noticed different kind of approaches dealing with ethics dilemmas. Thanks to Fromm's approach, today the Health Coach will be able to balance this tension in a more harmonious way, facilitating productivity or positive displacement of the social character.

Keywords: Health Coaching, Wellbeing, Ethics, Coaching Methodology, Performance.

*"Man's failure to use and spend what he possesses is the cause of illness and unhappiness. The validity of this principle appears with regard to both physical and psychic powers."
(Fromm, 1947)*

Aristotle defines well-being as eudaimonia. In his Nicomachean Ethics (Outsia, web), this human condition is an experience linked to the fulfilment of one or more virtuous acts, in accordance with one's rational nature, with one's choices. Wellbeing in the classic sense, therefore, depends on a particular type of action that brings to fruition the very nature of the individual. Other more recent thinkers seem to have taken over this view. Today we are faced with a dominant utilitarian thought that does not fully consider the meaning of individual well-being.

The need for an alternative response to this theme of well-being can come specifically from the innovative and radical model of Humanistic Transformation. Here we briefly report the salient points launched in the Panel of this 3rd International Erich Fromm Research Conference (Kuhn et al. 2023):

1 - A humanistic effective change needs to upgrade the relationship pattern. Each component of the society may find its **resonance** with the other parts. This will allow a safe space where a natural impulse of creativity and collaboration may flourish.

2 - Observing the contemporary world, sometimes we feel lost and pessimist. Actually, *Hope is not based on evidence*.

3 - Our Human heritage tell us that we are able to address every dramatic crisis, and each of us own this inner gift from the past generations. It's not about being optimistic or pessimistic, but **realistic** and ready to cope with resistance, complexity, ambiguity and uncertainty.

4 - The love for life (biophilia), is the main resource of our capability to generate an authentic pragmatic evolution in our society, facilitating growth and collaboration. Self- consciousness and awareness will drive our commitment to be engaged towards an ideal not in itself, but **for** itself.

5 - There is a human potential in the society that needs to be awakened. Each of us has a part of this potential hidden inside. That's why the pillar of the very first step of this evolution is: being a **catalyst** for this potential.

6 - The responsibility of what you CAN is in the hand of **participation**.

"Anything you can do, it's enough to endeavour a Humanistic Transformation"

This is the call to action launched in this Panel Discussion. This appeal derives from the previous series of considerations on the current situation which is important to report as premises, considering that they also affect our history as the Italian Health Coaching Association

My paper will illustrate how within the Italian Health Coaching Association (AIHC), the importance of re-establishing the identity of the Health Coach has emerged, with a view to an approach that prioritizes the interest of the person's well-being, because from our point of view the application of Coaching techniques in the dialectic of the "good life" today requires precise references to the Social Philosophy. With this presentation I intend to offer you a:

1 – contemporary example of Humanistic Transformation;

2 - a different and practical vision and perception of the world of individual values;

3 – some cases of Humanistic Ethics practice.

We hope with our Association that our reflection can also inspire further research, collaborations and applications. You will listen to the main assumptions of this kind of "alienated" perception which has opened a discussion in our Association, and then move on to a synthesis of our philological research and finally arrive at the current evidence which, from our point of view, has opened up a new perspective in the scope of our profession. At the end I will report some application examples, so, if there are curiosities and doubts, the potential impacts can be more tangible, clear and resonant.

Why is our Health Coaching Association interested in this topic?

AIHC is a national association recently born in 2017 (AIHC, web), driven by a growing demand for Health and Wellness. It brings together mainly, and not only, Professional Coaches engaged in the safeguarding and development of wellbeing in the healthcare system, in corporate organizations and at the individual level.

Indeed, according to what was discussed in the Coaching Labs, the methodological setting of coaching techniques seemed to be mainly based on Performance. Furthermore, when we found ourselves applying the Coaching techniques of our Schools, we perceived that something was wrong: we often had to go beyond the current methodology. It was as if the Health Coaches were followers of a change driven by some progressive practice facilitation techniques. Though applied, they missed an Ethic concept that could clearly guide a natural human transformation. There seemed to be a lack of a rational basis of the profession that would inspire the Coach in interpreting the ethical dilemmas in the Individual-Society relationship. Many Heads of Coaching Schools in recent decades have had brilliant intuitions in offering an ethical based support to the person, but none of them had offered an overall vision that was convincing, profound and complete, in outlining the basic and natural principles of generating individual well-being. In particular, in recent years, we have seen a "reactive" shift in the Coaching style, precisely in an attempt to respond to this growing demand for health. This "ethical shift" of Coaching has also been observed in Anglo-Saxon healthcare systems by Iordanou et al. (2017). That's why, basically, we felt incomplete as Health Coaches: because we lacked a fundamental identity in our methodological approach (Patania, 2022).

The perception of having moved far away from the roots of Performance Coaching, while maintaining its pragmatism and methodological scheme, is accompanied by a sometimes conflicting distance between Performance and Wellbeing, which the Health Coach is often inclined to facilitate in his client. This aspect is of such importance that it is now entering all systems with high performance demands, returning to the roots of Coaching, even in sport (Carlson et al. 2017). For this reason, as Health Coaches, we wanted to delve deeper into this approach to Coaching, reviewing all the major protagonists in truly taking care of wellbeing, in order to find common ethical denominators and find a point of reference that could be a model of inspiration for the Health Coach.

Neuroscience explains well what the advantages of a profound attitude of awareness of the operator are, given that the mental state selects external signals based on beliefs and personal experiences. The first to have this intuition was William James, who described how concentrating on one aspect of reality "involves the withdrawal of the mind from some things in order to be able to operate on others with great efficiency (James, 1890). Today we know that perceptual filters can be self-induced by endogenous cueing, in which the orientation of attention is voluntary, guided by the participant's goals (Gazzaniga et al., 2021). On the other hand, it is now well known that the social and emotional context has a strong prevalence on the moral behaviour of the individual (Valdesolo et al., 2006 and 2007). For this reason, it is important to have ethical models that guarantee the integrity of the person subjected to pressure from the external, as happens in moral distress and burn out to ensure behaviour aligned with one's real intention (Borg et al, 2006).

The need for a pure original intention relating to Health Coaching therefore seems to go far beyond a simple feeling of discomfort on the part of the operators. This profound need to have as a reference an "intentional" model different from the classic Performance-based Executive Coaching schools seems to be also confirmed by Pelham in 2015 and also reported by Iordanou et al in 2017: "a different *me* that you bring into the relationship (of coaching) will determine how you understand and deal with problems." In other words, it seems clear that the experiences, mentality, beliefs and cultural imprinting of the Health Coach influence his good intentions and in a second moment has an impact on the client. For this reason, greater clarity and inspiration of a Humanistic and Ethical model for Wellbeing will make Health Coaches much more effective in giving support to the person, precisely in the current most important challenge of the human being: his Humanistic Transformation.

I present to you the question of our professional identity crisis through three different perspectives of the Health Coach's activity, in a sort of zoom: we will start from the Mission, move on to the Mindset and finally arrive at the Setting.

1 MISSION - The key points of the Mission seem to have quite fully anticipated the themes we are developing today: empowerment, wellbeing, personal growth, subjective conscience, pro-activity, integrity and social responsibility. They are all present in the AIHC Mission and Values paper:

“empowerment, as a lever for the promotion of health and the expansion of people's spaces of well-being”

*“...supporting them both in **personal growth** and development and in the **consciously accepted subjective** adoption of lifestyles healthy, educating them to **actively manage their health condition**”*

*“sharing, **integrity and social responsibility**”*

It is as if the emerging conflict between the Executive approach and the person's needs pre-existed in our Health Coaching Mission. We found in this reflection confirmation that our critical approach respected our Vision and was in line with our social task.

2 MINDSET – The recent 2021 update of the Coaching Competencies by the International Coaching Federation has also encouraged our critical reflection on the identity of the Health Coach, with particular regard to the mindset. The ICF indication is very clear in this regard (ICF, website):

*“Embodies a Coaching Mindset” highlights the value of focusing on yourself as a coach and provides guidance **on how to invest in “being” a coach** (alongside “doing” the coaching)*

“how to invest in BEING a Coach” is about Being, a matter of Identity, confirming our previous reflections on “the intention to be a proper health coach”.

And the following ICF sentence could very well be taken from a Fromm essay (ICF, website):

“Be aware of how your own background may have influenced who you are as an individual”

Therefore, confirming not only our right to question previous models of Coaching, but even our duty to constantly maintain the awareness that our past must be seen with a critical professional conscience, in the interest of our role and in the guarantee of our client.

Thus, with the confirmation that our debate on AIHC identity was based on solid ethical and professional documents regarding the Mission and the Mindset, we moved on to analyze the real phenomenon: the session Setting with all its dynamics and contents.

3 SETTING - This comparison is a-posteriori, obtained thanks to our critical analysis. At the beginning we ignored many of these aspects and only felt a certain discomfort. As I said, we often found ourselves needing to go deeper into giving support to the individual, looking for the deeper meaning of situations. Fromm describes this condition very well when in "A Man for himself"(1947). He explains the difference between intelligence and reason: the first is bi-dimensional, the second adds to these dimensions a third one: the sense of purpose. Intelligence is used to obtain practical results, defined in a bi-dimensional quantitative way. The practical example of this setting is the management goals SMART model (Doran, 1981). This kind of approach in line with the previous high-performance management concepts. This methodology addressing management with measurable goals was popularized by Peter Drucker (1954) as Management by Objectives (MBO), also called Management by Results (MBR). This methodology gave for granted every purpose, simply not considering it. It's only a matter of bi-dimensional intelligence, where cognitive skills and problem-solving rule and the effect is immediate. Reason is not only two-dimensional (achievement of results and quantitative aspect), but three-dimensional and prospective, since it adds a sense of purpose to the practical sense. That's why reason consider the individual point of view and the personal healthy interest. Exactly the Health Coaching matter. From this fundamental premise, other aspects also emerge that make the experience of classic Coaching (Executive) different from that which is interested in Wellbeing. I report in this list some of the differential aspects that can be read in the two different activities, thanks to a greater social awareness. It's simply a matter of focus. For example, if Executive Coaching deal with Goal oriented results in the Future, Health Coaching it's about the present condition of the personal emotional and physical state. In line with the main Erich Fromm pillars, the health coach promotes the critical awareness of the person, removing the hypnotic pressure towards the myth of success, to promote the healthy and authentic development of the person (Fromm, 1961). In line with this concept, the Health Coach act in the present personal state to achieve a long term adherence to authentic life, thanks to the productive behaviour (Fromm, 1947). Another important difference is to respect the sense of limit. In contemporary society the tendency is to erase the personal perception of one's limits (and one's identity) (Funk, 2020). In the past, this methodological deficiency, due to the flat bi-dimensional plan of action, has often caused a superficial and harmful management of the value system of the individual and of communities and companies in support of coaching, negatively affecting personal and organizational well-being (Dolan e Renaud, 1992; Dolan, 2007).

Classic Coaching setting	Health Coaching setting
* Intelligence driven - 2D (SMART)	* Reason driven - 3D
* Immediate	* Perspective
* Performance centered	* Wellbeing centered
* Functionalist	* Holistic
* Goal oriented	* State oriented
* Success oriented	* Health oriented
* Resilience	* Adherence
* Peak experience	* Pain experience
* Cancel limits (and borders)	* Challenge limits (respect borders)

It is now very clear why the tension between these two elements of performance and well-being generated an ethical-value misalignment in the identity of Health Coaching. Today the incompatibility of these two systems is clear, when considered in their exclusive polarity.

Now that we have made the three dimensions Mission, Mindset, setting legible, let's add another element of contemporary reading. What significantly worsens the effects of this Executive-Health incompatibility is social acceleration. In this, Coaching represents a very important element and deserves every attention. The Health Coach, actually applies a functional deceleration (Rosa, 2010) through which he fits into the frenetic pace of the individual's life, to propose deep three-dimensional perspective reflections that allow to recover the sense of purpose, to learn and correct one's behaviours in productive sense. This *liminal space* (Neuman & Temple, 2022) that suspends space and time is one opportunity for the person to explore values, purpose and get learning to be naturally productive.

To give greater solidity to this reflection, we move on to present our philological study which has allowed us to achieve greater awareness of the context and of our professional role.

From this debate in the Coaching Lab 2022 in Turin, where the foundations had already been laid for a critical analysis, guided precisely by Fromm's thought, the idea of the philological research we are observing was born, carried out in three successive levels with a progressive investigation.

We reserved the research to Coaching methodologies, identifying those methodologies that we defined as "reactive", as they began to deviate from the classic model, trying to give an answer to the need for wellbeing that was progressively growing.

Once the main authors of these Coaching techniques have been identified, we have analyzed the specific matter, the key points in the **nature** of these "reactive" methodologies: **Ethics**. The past attempt of coaching techniques in ethical change has been to resolve this tension, mainly by working on values. We have noticed different types of approaches that address ethical dilemmas.

In the third level we went back to researching the literature on Coaching, until we went beyond the years of its foundation and went back to the primordial source of the methodological principles of Objective Humanistic Ethics, described for the first time and in an ingenious and exhaustive way in 1947 by Erich Fromm in his investigation into the psychology of morals. To the vision of ethical change, our observation added valuable elements not addressed before and a more ontological and humanistic interpretation (Patania, 2023).

To understand the overall nature of the phenomenon, our research has positioned the main protagonists of this ethical turning point of Coaching along the distribution of the different types of coaching formed, going back to the first authors of the Coaching methodology. In selecting these models, the “Values” element was identified as a common feature. This allowed us to consolidate the sample and exclude other types of approaches. In this way, we had confirmation of having selected the most significant models among those aimed at the "reactive" shift from Performance towards individual well-being (Barrett, 1998, 2006, 2014) (Dolan et al., 2006, 2020) (Dilts, 1990, 2003, Dilts et al., 2012)(Maslow, 1968)(Ben Arzi, 2022).

Considering that a substantial alignment of all "reactive" Life Coaching movements on the topic of Values has emerged, the research space has expanded to the area that contains the Values and derives fundamental Norms and Principles from them: respectively Morality and above all 'Ethics. A search was carried out for works dedicated to Coaching that specifically addressed the Ethics – Coaching combination.

The second level research confirmed the hypotheses and thanks to a publication by Iourdanou et al. (Values & Ethics in Coaching, 2017), there was confirmation of the empirical observation made on the Values models of the first phase. In the initial observation, the one that inspired the research, there was the perception of some "reactive shift" of Coaching techniques towards an evolution in favour of Wellbeing. Our observation was confirmed and bibliographed by this publication. Iordanou et al. describe the "shift" from Performance Coaching to Life Coaching. The adaptive push of the emerging needs of the evolving UK healthcare system has produced innovative thinking where from "doing to" a "doing with" was hoped for, with greater collaborative involvement of caregivers and patients. This new model has gradually produced a spontaneous transformation of formal and informal coaching that is increasingly closer to the person. In the words of the three authors, a path towards "more ethical" coaching.

A further observation revealed how the general foundations of the method were generally compatible with the thinking of the exponents of the "third force" of psychology, and in particular of Erich Fromm, the only one to deal rigorously and completely with ethical analysis of personality developmental dynamics. From our point of view, what makes Fromm the point of reference is that through objective humanistic ethics, he demonstrates his full trust in human nature and links it to the development of potential and well-being (Fromm, 1963). He supports humanity's natural

tendency to be productive and healthy (Fromm, 1947). On the other hand, it exactly describes the polarity between the individual and society as a dynamic tension between two forces: the performance required of the individual by the social system, and the person's tendency towards his own well-being, from an ethical point of view. Thanks to Fromm's approach, today the Health Coach will be able to balance this tension in a more harmonious way, facilitating productivity or the positive shift of the social character.

All the authors indicated, in fact, had a pragmatic and empirical approach to the use of the Values, without framing them in an Ethical methodological analysis. They have created models for the beneficial use of Values, without explaining the reasons in depth and without including a rigorous sociological, systemic and ethical analysis.

The Humanist framework, the rationale for this whole movement is provided by Erich Fromm in his “moral psychological analysis” (Fromm, 1947).

Regarding the identity of Health Coaching, finding an original rationale in social philosophy related to the Mission, the Mindset and the Setting offers the answer to the question of belonging of all Wellness Operators. All this will make the expansion of the space dedicated to the well-being of patients, caregivers, healthcare workers and organizations more aware and powerful. On the other hand, as regards specifically all the techniques that involve the use of Values in Facilitation, therefore on an ethical basis, these will benefit from an even stronger and more rooted conceptual reference, and it is foreseeable that this fact will open up new avenues of application. Furthermore,

*"man cannot live without values and norms,
such relativism makes him easy prey to irrational systems of values...
The great tradition of humanistic ethical thought has laid the foundations of the **system of values**
founded on autonomy and human **reason**".*

For Fromm, Humanistic Ethics is science applied to the Art of Living.

And Human Reason is its tool.

The philological research carried out by the AIHC scientific committee was published in a neuroscience journal NEU and confirmed with its own observation the scheme proposed by Iordanou et al. related to the ethical change of coaching techniques in health systems, with the opportunities of many useful applications.

ABSTRACT

PURPOSE AND TYPE OF RESEARCH

The aim of the research is to discover effective tools to support and educate caregivers in the face of difficult situations, including from an ethical point of view, such as moral distress.

A literature review devoted to the link between moral behavior and neuroscience was performed. Subsequently, the main models of Coaching with Ethical purposes were studied, as a progressive detachment from the Coaching model linked to Performance. Once the affinities were established, a philological research was carried out among the main authors of Humanistic Ethics to identify the authentic roots of a Health Coaching aimed at defining the fundamental principles of an enhancement of Well-being.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on Neuroscience, a decisive link has emerged between moral behavior and emotional impact, with tangible implications on the caregiver's resilience. The main Coaching schools of thought that have taken into consideration the well-being of the person have turned to the configuration of Values, that

is, to ethical and moral principles. Through the empirical observation that excess performance in organizations generated problems for individual Well-being, each of the main protagonists of this "reactive" Coaching, faced the same problem based on different points of view: the inner dilemma based on Values.

A rationale common to these authors was sought in the social philosophy literature, recognizing in the works of Erich Fromm the main inspirer of deontological Health Coaching, based on the priority of support for the person.

CONCLUSIONS

Thanks to this evidence, the possibility opens up of further deepening the study of Fromm's school of social philosophy and relating it to caregiver support techniques, so that the strengthening intervention makes use of a greater technical awareness of the dynamics underlying the inner moral conflict.

Key Words

Caregiver, Moral Distress, Health Coaching, Humanistic Ethics, Well-being.

One confirmation of our position comes from the world of Healthcare, where Maccoby's work proposed a model of Healthcare Learning Organization, and the manager's leadership is exercised in a purely Humanistic way. The Health Coach can also take fundamental cues from this model in order to be able to interact effectively with the Healthcare Organizations (Maccoby et al., 2013):

« They discover that **the human side**,
the different ways people process information,
their **values** and attitudes,
can either facilitate or block learning...*

Demonstrate that you are a synthesizer or better yet a **humanizer**
rather than merely an analyzer or energizer
by participating in the interactive dialogue
and defining part of your work as
the **development of people and teams.**”*

**healthcare managers*

On the basis of all this, we can provocatively and instrumentally hypothesize a *Humanistic Secession* of Health Coaching from the traditional one, which concerns not so much the techniques or the methodological approach, rather than a more radical MISSION, MINDSET, SETTING.

HEALTH COACHING HUMANISTIC SECESSION

- 1 – far away from Coaching Paternalism/Sensationalism
- 2 – towards the Integrity of Human Natural Core
- 3 – avoiding cultural tags (success, life/work balance, diversity...)
- 4 - unleashing the deep authenticity and uniqueness of the person and his personal history
- 5 – out of the manipulation of the temporal totalitarianism/presentism
- 6 - taking “anonymous authority” pressure in account
- 7 – facilitating a natural resonance of the person in giving him back responsibility
- 8 – eliciting in the person a sense of their own boundaries

One further example of the application of a Humanistic approach to conscious Health Coaching, which can finally access concepts of humanistic social philosophy, improving one's own professional approach, is the following. According with the concept of methodological expansion, which precisely concern Fromm's school, a Coaching approach on Values, it could be enlightened by the concept of *dissolution of boundaries* described by Rainer Funk (2011), in the Ego-oriented character. By bringing Health Coaching within the scope of Humanistic critical thinking, every type of individual-society interaction phenomenon becomes much clearer and the facilitation action much more aware and effective.

Dissolution-Spillover (Entgrenzung) (Funk)	Human Core identity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Autonomous alignment * Ausiliary Self * Disengagement from internal regulatory systems * Moral Relativism from Community Values and do-gooders * Deresponsability/alienation * Emotional mimetism/simulation * Moral defeat/solitude 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Natural alignment * Authentic Self * Processing, interpretation and choice within the internal regulatory system * Moral laws from Core Values and Inner directives * Accountability * Emotional authenticity * Moral choice/sharing

From the proposed scheme it is clear that the Health Coach must be aware of many distorted forms of limiting beliefs that can derive from the Ego-oriented character. It is the social belief system that puts pressure on the individual and the Health Coach must be aware of being subject to this dynamic himself. Its primary task is to free itself from this factionalism. Many of the threats to objectivity and impartiality in promoting personal well-being arise from anonymous authority. That form of conformist pressure that is multiplied by social relations and the mass media.

The Health Coach must be well aware that he, like his client, is subjected to this pressure. His defence weapon is curiosity combined with a critical spirit and reason.

*"It's disguised as common sense,
science, mental health, normality, public opinion.
It requires nothing more than evidence.
He doesn't seem to use any pressure but only gentle persuasion..."*

*On anonymous authority,
both the command and the commander became invisible.
It's like being attacked by an invisible enemy.
There is no one and nothing to fight against."
(Fromm, 1961)*

We conclude this discussion taking inspiration from Prof. Kuhn's communication in this Conference (2023) on the importance of the Humanistic Transformation and the Revolution of Hope advocated by Erich Fromm (1968). Certainly, many of the answers about our Future depend on questions. If we said that hope is not a matter of evidence, then we can use creative models that describe the impact of media innovation. One of these was created by Mc Luhan (Mc Luhan & Mc Luhan, 2017) and can be useful for predicting the impact of a Humanistic Coaching approach to digitalization. We share here this proposal that expands the teaching methodology in medical schools to a doctor-patient relationship that is broader and less notional. Here too the human authenticity of the doctor interprets Digital Humanism as a resource for evolving towards a doctor-algorithm collaboration, and the corresponding McLuhan tetrad presents, as always, some surprises (Patania, 2023).

We hope with our AIHC Association that our discussion can also inspire further research, collaborations and applications in addressing the tension between personal growth and social needs.

Bibliography

1. Barrett R. (1998) *Liberating the corporate soul: building a visionary organization*, Butterworth-Heinemann
2. Barrett R. (2006) *Building a Value Driven Organization*, Routledge
3. Barrett R. (2014) *Evolutionary coaching*, Lulu Pub. Serv.
4. Borg J.S., Hynes C., Van Horn J., Grafton S., Sinnott-Armstrong W. (2006) *Consequences, Action, and Intention as Factors in Moral Judgments: An FMRI Investigation*, Journal of Cognitive Science, 18(5):803-17
5. Carson, F.; Walsh, J.; Main, C.M. and Kremer, P. (2017) “*High performance Coaches’ mental health and wellbeing: applying the areas of work life model*” International Sport Coaching Journal, Vol. 5 issue 3 pg 202-300
6. Dilts R. (1990) *Changing beliefs system with NLP* – Middle English Ed
7. Dilts R. (2003) *From Coach to awakener*, Meta publications
8. Dilts, R., Hallborn, T., Smith, S. (2012) “*Beliefs*” - 2’ ed. -Crowne House Publishing Ltd.
9. Dolan S. L. (2007) “*The Role of Personality and Social Support in the Aetiology of Workers’ Stress and Psychological Strain*”, Industrial Relations (Canada), 47(1)
10. Dolan S.L., Renaud S. (1992) *Individual, organizational and social determinants of managerial burnout - Journal of Social Behaviour and Personality*; Corte Madera, CA vol. 7 Iss.1
11. Dolan S.L., Garcia S., Richley B. (2006) *Managing by values*, Palgrave MacMillan
12. Dolan S.L., Valeri P., Mele M. (2020) *Leadership management e coaching dei valori*, Gestion MDS Inc.
13. Doran, G. T. (1981). “*There’s a SMART way to write management’s goals and objectives*”. *Management Review*. 70 (11): 35–36.
14. Drucker, P.F. (1954) *Practice of Management*, Harper
15. Fromm, E. (1947) “*A man for Himself*”, Rinehart
16. Fromm, E. (1961) “*Escape from Freedom*” Holt, Rinehart and Winston
17. Fromm, E. (1963) “*The Art of Loving*” Bantam
18. Fromm, E. (1968) “*The revolution of Hope: towards a humanized technology*”- Ruth Nanda Ashen ed.
19. Funk, R. (2011) *The Ego-Oriented Man and His Strivings Erich Fromm’s Social Characterological Concept of Man and Its Relevance for Today* - Journal of Philosophical Anthropology, Volgograd, Vol. 1, issue 3, pp. 107-123
20. Funk, R. (2020) “*L’uomo sconfinato*” – Sensibili alle foglie
21. Gazzaniga M., Poeppel D., Mangun G.R. (2020) “*The Cognitive Neurosciences*” - MIT PRESS ltd
22. Iordanou, I., Hawley, R., Iordanou, C. (2017) “*Values and Ethics in Coaching*” Sage
23. James W. (1890) – *The principles of psychology*, Henry Holt and C.
24. Kuhn, T. (2023) *The importance of Humanistic Transformation from a psychological perspective*– 3rd International Erich Fromm Conference – Berlin
25. Kuhn, T.; Gesine, S.; Welzer, H.; Bruhn, T. and Hofielen, G. (2023) *Panel Discussion on Humanistic Transformation* – 3rd International Erich Fromm Conference – Berlin
26. Maccoby, M., Norman C.L., Norman, C.J., Margolies, R. (2013) *Transforming Health Care Leadership* – Jossey Bass
27. Mc Luhan M., Mc Luhan, E. (2017) “*The lost tetrads of Marshall Mc Luhan*” OR Books
28. Maslow A. H. (1968) “*Towards a psychology of being*”, Litton Educational Publishing ltd.
29. Neumann, K.D. (2022) “*Liminal space: what it is and how does it affect your mental health*” Forbes Health
30. Patania, S.L. (2022) “*Erich Fromm and the Health Coach Identity*” – Turin October 8th 2022 – AIHC Meeting Lab. (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375576955_Erich_Fromm_and_the_Health_Coaching_Identity)
31. Patania, S.L. (2023) “*Le radici Umanistiche dell’Health Coaching*” - NEU – Rivista ANIN - 1° Marzo 2023 <https://www.anin.it/Riviste.aspx>
32. Patania. S.L. (2023) “*Verso una Futurizzazione ed Umanizzazione delle cure. La Metodologia Clinica si ispira ad un Umanesimo Digitale*” - MedMagazine, Anno VII, num. 1 <https://medmagazine.info/>
33. Pelham G. (2015) *The coaching relationship in practice*, Sage
34. Rosa, H. (2010) *Alienation and Acceleration: Towards a Critical Theory of Late Modern Temporality* Aarhus Universitetsforlag
35. Valdesolo P., De Steno D., (2007) *Moral ipocrisy: social groups and the flexibility of virtue* - Psychological Science, 18(8):689-90
36. Valdesolo P., De Steno D., (2006). *Manipulations of Emotional Context Shape Moral Judgment*. Psychological Science, 17(6), 476–477

Websites

- Aristotele, *Etica Nicomachea* (1099a 10, 15): <http://www.ousia.it/content/Sezioni/Testi/AristoteleEticaNicomachea.pdf>
AIHC: <https://www.aihc.it/mission-e-carta-dei-valori/>
Ben-Arzi, S. (2022) <https://www.peoplebuilders.com.au/blog/emotional-intelligence-in-the-context-of-a-medical-crisis>
International Coaching Federation: <https://coachingfederation.org/blog/embodies-a-coaching-mindset>